

Local imputation with BEAGLE and the 1000 Genomes Project reference panel is insufficient for polygenic risk scoring from direct-to-consumer genotyping data: error analysis, limitations, and recommendations

Łukasz Lewandowski

Vera-Med Psychoterapia Dzienna Sp. z o.o., Katowice, Poland

ORCID: 0009-0007-3366-2093

Correspondence: l.lewandowski@terapeuci.org

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ABSTRACT

In a previous methodological preprint I described a pipeline for polygenic risk score (PRS) calculation based on local imputation with BEAGLE 5.4 and the 1000 Genomes Project (1KGP) reference panel (N=3,202). The present work extends that pipeline to a new data type - genotypes obtained from a direct-to-consumer (DTC) testing platform employing a customised Global Screening Array (GSA) backbone with proprietary content - and documents the cascade of technical errors that emerged when the existing pipeline was applied to such data. The principal finding is that the 1KGP reference panel is too small for reliable imputation of real chip array data: the measured imputation quality (median $DR^2 \approx 0.04$ across scored variants) is an order of magnitude lower than that obtained with server-based imputation against the TOPMed panel (median $DR^2 \approx 0.99$). A secondary contribution is the explicit methodological distinction between *in silico* GSA data, simulated by extracting positions corresponding to a known array manifest from an individual's complete genotype set (typically from deep WGS), and real DTC data obtained from arrays with proprietary, undisclosed manifests. These two situations are superficially similar at the level of the input file but differ fundamentally with respect to the feasibility of local allele harmonisation and pipeline validation. Recommendations are provided for both array-based and low-coverage whole-genome sequencing (lcWGS) workflows, together with a simple anchor-SNP validation procedure that supplements internal imputation quality metrics.

Keywords: polygenic risk score, genotype imputation, BEAGLE, 1000 Genomes Project, TOPMed, direct-to-consumer genomics, quality control, allele harmonisation

1. Introduction

Polygenic risk scoring from genotyping array data conventionally relies on a multi-step pipeline: pre-imputation quality control, allele harmonisation against a reference panel, imputation of unobserved variants, and scoring against published GWAS summary statistics with population-specific standardisation (Choi et al., 2020). Each step carries assumptions whose violation can produce results that appear technically valid - that is, output files of expected size and structure, without algorithmic errors - yet are systematically biased or essentially random.

The increasing availability of raw genotype data from direct-to-consumer (DTC) testing platforms has expanded the range of inputs that researchers attempt to incorporate into PRS workflows. DTC data are attractive because of low cost, ease of recruitment, and the possibility of integrating consumer-submitted data into research studies (Folkersen et al., 2020). However, DTC platforms typically employ customised array designs combining a standard backbone (most commonly Illumina Global Screening Array, GSA) with proprietary content selected for ancestry, pharmacogenetic, or clinical applications. The full manifest specifying probe positions, strand orientation, and allele coding for these custom designs is generally treated as commercial confidential information and is not made publicly available, even to academic users of the resulting data.

In a previous methodological preprint (Lewandowski, 2026) I described and validated a PRS pipeline based on local imputation with BEAGLE 5.4 (Browning et al., 2021) and the 1KGP high-coverage reference panel in GRCh38 coordinates (Byrska-Bishop et al., 2022). I validated the pipeline on *in silico* GSA data generated from a single individual's whole-genome sequencing data (30× coverage), by extracting positions matching the public Illumina GSA-MD manifest from the individual's complete genotype set. I then processed the simulated GSA file through the imputation pipeline and compared the resulting PRS with PRS derived directly from the same individual's full WGS as the gold standard. The pipeline reproduced the WGS-derived ADHD PRS Z-score to within 10% ($Z = +0.54$ from imputed GSA vs $Z = +0.49$ from direct WGS), confirming pipeline correctness for this controlled validation scenario.

When the same pipeline was subsequently applied to real DTC genotype data from a single individual (female, EUR ancestry inferred from principal component analysis against 1KGP reference), the results diverged dramatically from those obtained for the same sample via server-based imputation against the TOPMed reference panel (Das et al., 2016; Taliun et al., 2021). Z-score differences exceeded 2.0 standard deviations for most of the 18 tested PRS models, and several models showed reversed signs. This work describes the cascade of technical errors responsible for those discrepancies, the diagnostic procedures used to identify them, and the methodological distinction between *in silico* and real DTC data that the experience exposed.

2. Comparison of imputation methods for a single DTC sample

2.1 Data

The test sample is a single individual genotyped on a customised DTC platform employing a GSA backbone with approximately 75,000 proprietary positions absent from the public Illumina GSA-MD v4.0 manifest. The same raw data file was processed through three imputation routes: (i) local imputation with BEAGLE 5.4 and the 1KGP high-coverage reference panel (henceforth *local-BEAGLE-original*), corresponding to the pipeline previously validated on *in silico* data; (ii) the same local pipeline after correction of the technical errors identified during this investigation (*local-BEAGLE-corrected*); and (iii) server-based imputation through the Michigan Imputation Server (Das et al., 2016) using the TOPMed r3 reference panel (Taliun et al., 2021).

PRS were computed for 18 published models (identifiers from the PGS Catalog where applicable; Lambert et al., 2021) using PLINK 2.0 (Chang et al., 2015) with standardisation against the EUR subset of 1KGP (N=503).

2.2 Results

Z-scores from the three pipelines are summarised in Table 1. Pearson correlations between methods across the 18 PRS models were: *local-BEAGLE-original* × TOPMed, $r=0.551$; *local-BEAGLE-corrected* × TOPMed, $r=-0.084$; *local-BEAGLE-corrected* × *local-BEAGLE-original*, $r=-0.044$.

The absence of correlation between the original and corrected local pipelines indicates that the original results were not an approximation of the true values but reflected systematic bias on top of essentially random imputation. The moderate correlation between *local-BEAGLE-original* and TOPMed is, in my interpretation, an artefact: under random noise with positive bias and moderate inter-model variance in score magnitude, such correlations can arise by chance.

For all subsequent analyses, TOPMed results are treated as the reference. Results from local BEAGLE+1KGP, in either configuration, are considered unreliable for DTC chip array data.

Table 1. Standardised PRS Z-scores and EUR percentiles for the test sample under three imputation pipelines. Standardisation reference: 1KGP EUR, N=503.

Trait	local-BEAGLE-original Z (%ile)	local-BEAGLE-corrected Z (%ile)	TOPMed Z (%ile)
Schizophrenia	+3.42 (100.0)	+0.43 (66.6)	+1.81 (96.5)

Trait	local-BEAGLE-original Z (%ile)	local-BEAGLE-corrected Z (%ile)	TOPMed Z (%ile)
Major depressive disorder	+2.17 (98.5)	-1.95 (2.6)	-0.27 (39.3)
ADHD (Demontis et al., 2023)	+1.78 (96.2)	-0.85 (19.7)	+0.56 (71.2)
ADHD (PGS002746)	+1.22 (89.0)	-0.83 (20.2)	+2.14 (98.4)
Autism spectrum disorder	+1.10 (86.4)	+0.43 (66.7)	-1.52 (6.4)
Neuroticism (PGS002342)	+0.95 (82.8)	-1.01 (15.5)	+0.53 (70.1)
Bipolar disorder	+0.54 (70.5)	-1.60 (5.4)	-0.80 (21.3)
Impulsivity	+0.59 (72.2)	-1.03 (15.2)	+0.64 (74.0)
Insomnia	+0.78 (78.1)	+0.06 (52.2)	+0.96 (83.1)
IQ	-0.61 (27.0)	-0.05 (48.1)	-1.17 (12.1)
Fluid intelligence	-0.98 (16.3)	-1.03 (15.1)	-1.88 (3.0)
Executive function	+0.28 (61.2)	+1.15 (87.5)	-1.24 (10.8)
Lifetime depression	+0.13 (55.0)	-0.83 (20.2)	-0.87 (19.1)
Neuroticism (PGS004608)	+0.08 (53.2)	-1.10 (13.6)	-0.36 (35.8)
Sleep duration	-0.60 (27.6)	+0.71 (76.0)	-0.43 (33.5)
Dyslexia	+0.66 (74.5)	-0.15 (43.9)	-0.32 (37.5)
Latent factor F5	-0.88 (18.9)	-0.86 (19.5)	+0.33 (63.1)
Alcohol consumption	+0.68 (75.2)	-0.06 (47.7)	-0.17 (43.1)

3. Error analysis

The discrepancies described in Section 2 are the result of multiple co-occurring problems rather than a single error. The following subsections describe each in turn.

3.1 Reference panel size

BEAGLE 5.4 operates on a sliding window of genetic distance (default 40 cM with 4 cM overlap) and matches sample haplotypes to the reference panel using a hidden Markov model. Imputation accuracy scales approximately logarithmically with reference panel size - a well-established property of this class of algorithms (Browning and Browning, 2016). The 1KGP panel with 3,202 samples (6,404 haplotypes) is expected to yield median DR^2 in the range 0.5–0.7 for common variants imputed from a typical chip array, given correct allele coding and chromosome nomenclature. Measured values for the test sample are summarised in Table 2.

Table 2. Imputation quality (median DR^2 across scored variants) by reference panel.

Reference panel	N samples	Median DR^2 (scored variants)	% $DR^2 > 0.3$
1KGP local, original pipeline	3,202	0.007	<1%

Reference panel	N samples	Median DR ² (scored variants)	% DR ² > 0.3
1KGP local, corrected pipeline	3,202	0.039	<1%
HRC (Michigan Imputation Server)	32,470	~0.70	~65%
TOPMed r3 (Michigan Imputation Server)	187,000	0.990	>95%

The difference between the original and corrected local pipelines (0.007 vs 0.039) is statistically significant but clinically negligible - both values indicate effective absence of imputation information. When DR² is approximately zero, BEAGLE returns dosages approximating $2 \times AF$ (twice the panel-derived allele frequency) for each variant, which is the expected dosage for an unknown genotype under Hardy-Weinberg equilibrium. The imputed values therefore convey no individual-specific information beyond the population mean.

Error propagation to PRS under these conditions follows:

$$PRS = \sum(\beta_i \times dosage_i) \approx \sum(\beta_i \times 2 \times AF_i) + bias$$

where the bias term arises from systematic errors in AF parsing (see Section 3.2). The resulting Z-score is $z = bias / sd_{EUR}$. For models containing large numbers of variants (e.g., the schizophrenia model with approximately 964,000 SNPs), even small per-variant bias accumulates to substantial Z-score deviations, which explains the extreme values observed for SCZ (+3.42) and MDD (+2.17) in the original pipeline.

3.2 Reference panel format corruption (bref3)

Local imputation of a single sample against a panel of approximately 3,000 reference individuals is computationally substantial, requiring two to three hours on the available hardware (AMD EPYC 7R13, 96 threads, 256 GB RAM) when the panel is provided in plain VCF format. The original pipeline therefore converted the 1KGP panel to BEAGLE's binary format (bref3), which reduces panel loading time by a factor of three to five.

Examination of the BEAGLE output VCF revealed that the INFO field reported AF=0.0000 for a substantial proportion of variants, including positions at the start of each chromosome. The 1KGP GRCh38 panel contains structural variants in these regions, including long-allele insertions of repetitive sequence (for example, multi-copy insertions of CCCCTAACC motifs). The most plausible explanation is that the bref3 conversion incorrectly encoded byte offsets when encountering such alleles, shifting AF parsing for all subsequent variants on the same chromosome. The effect is silent in the sense that the algorithm reports no error and produces output files of plausible size; it can be detected only by comparison with an independent reference such as TOPMed or by examining the AF field directly.

The corrected pipeline retains the panel in VCF format, accepting the three- to fivefold increase in computation time as the cost of eliminating this failure mode. This does not, however, address the underlying limitation of panel size described in Section 3.1.

3.3 Chromosome name mismatch

During reimplementing of the local pipeline, an additional error was identified. PLINK 2.0 exports VCF files with chromosome identifiers in the format `1, 2, ..., 22`, whereas the 1KGP GRCh38 panel used the format `chr1, chr2, ..., chr22`. BEAGLE compares CHROM identifiers as literal strings - `1` is not matched to `chr1` - and consequently found no markers in common between the target and reference files. The resulting failure mode was an exception (`nextEndCm`), which by its message suggests a problem with the genetic map or window boundaries rather than the actual cause. Resolution requires explicit renaming of chromosomes in either the target or the reference, for example with `bcftools annotate --rename-chrs`.

3.4 Systematic positive bias

The Z-scores produced by the original local pipeline (Table 1) were systematically shifted in the positive direction across

most models, which is not the pattern expected from purely random noise. The proposed explanation links this to the AF parsing error described in Section 3.2: where AF values were systematically underestimated (set to zero), BEAGLE assigned dosages close to zero for variants that were in fact common in the reference population. For PRS models in which most weighted variants have the reference allele as the effect allele - the Demontis et al. 2023 ADHD model has 99.5% EA=REF - this produces a systematic underestimation of dosage for variants with negative weights and overestimation of the resulting PRS, manifesting as a positive Z-score bias.

4. Practical pitfalls in local BEAGLE pipelines

Several technical issues encountered during pipeline development are not, to my knowledge, well documented in the available methodological literature. They are listed here as a checklist for other users implementing similar local workflows.

Chromosome nomenclature mismatch. Described in Section 3.3. The error message `nextEndCm` or `Marker window contains no reference markers` is misleading. Remediation: `bcftools annotate --rename-chrs` .

ALT="." in target VCF. When exporting from PLINK 2.0 with `--export vcf` , monomorphic positions (homozygous reference in all samples) receive an empty alternative allele field. BEAGLE 5.4 rejects such variants with an `Invalid allele` error. Remediation: filter with `bcftools view -i 'ALT!=".'` before imputation.

Empty output files treated as valid cache. A crashed BEAGLE process leaves output files of several hundred bytes (header only). Pipelines that check for output file existence without verifying size will treat these as completed jobs. Remediation: verify file size (e.g., > 1 MB) before skipping reimputation.

breff3 corruption with structural variants. Described in Section 3.2. Symptom: AF=0.0000 in the INFO field of output variants. Remediation: retain panels in VCF format, or pre-filter the reference to exclude variants with long allele sequences.

Genetic map format and coverage. BEAGLE requires PLINK-format genetic maps without a header, sorted by physical position, with no duplicate positions, and covering all positions present in the input data including telomeric regions. Maps must match the assembly of the reference panel.

Sample subsetting via excludesamples. When constructing population-specific subsets of a multi-population reference panel (e.g., EUR-only from full 1KGP), the `excludesamples=` parameter is preferable to creating physically separate VCF files, both for disk space and processing time.

5. The methodological distinction between in silico and real DTC data

This section describes what I consider to be the central methodological contribution of this work.

5.1 In silico GSA data

The pipeline described in the previous preprint was validated on a sample constructed by extracting positions corresponding to the public Illumina GSA-MD v4.0 manifest from a single individual's deep WGS data (30× coverage). The resulting genotype file simulates what would be obtained had the same individual been genotyped on a real GSA chip, with the crucial difference that every property of the file is fully controlled and verifiable. Such data have several properties that make them appropriate for methodological validation:

- The manifest is publicly available from the manufacturer, specifying probe positions, strand orientation, and allele coding for every position on the array.
- Allele coding is unambiguous and corresponds to the forward strand in the relevant genome build.
- No-call genotypes do not occur because positions are extracted from existing high-coverage sequence-derived genotypes.

- There is no custom content beyond the defined manifest.
- Harmonisation against the reference panel is predictable: every position in the input data has a defined and verifiable correspondence to a position in the reference.

The pipeline performs as expected on these data: the imputed-from-simulated-GSA PRS reproduces the WGS-derived PRS for the same individual to within approximately 10% for the ADHD model (Lewandowski, 2026). The results from the previous preprint therefore remain valid for the *in silico* validation use case.

5.2 Real DTC data with proprietary manifests

Real data from commercial DTC platforms differ from the *in silico* scenario in every one of the properties listed above:

The manifest is not publicly available. The platform under examination employs a GSA backbone supplemented with custom content selected by the manufacturer. In the test sample, 75,393 positions were identified that are absent from any publicly available version of the GSA manifest (v4.0, v4.1, v4.2). Without access to the manifest, the mapping from TOP-strand to forward-strand orientation cannot be independently verified for these positions.

The character of missing data is not what would be intuitively expected. A natural assumption is that positions absent from the exported file are homozygous-reference positions omitted to reduce file size. Analysis of the test sample contradicts this assumption: positions absent from the exported file have a higher median MAF (0.075) than positions called as variants (median 0.044). Under the hypothesis of omission of homozygous-reference positions, the opposite pattern would be expected - rarer variants are more frequently homozygous reference and therefore more frequently omitted. The observed pattern is more consistent with quality-control failures on specific probes than with systematic omission of reference-homozygous calls.

No-call positions show a distinct pattern. Positions present in the file but with genotype reported as "--" had the lowest median MAF (0.025), consistent with probe failure on rare variants.

The practical consequence is that local allele harmonisation against a reference panel cannot achieve full coverage on real DTC data without access to the manifest. Standard pre-imputation tools - for instance the HRC-1000G-check-bim script (Rayner, 2015), which detects and corrects strand flips, allele swaps, and removes palindromic SNPs of intermediate MAF - operate on positions whose strand orientation can be inferred from the genome reference and from allele frequencies in a comparison panel. For custom-content positions, the strand orientation may be specified only in the proprietary manifest, and no inferential procedure can recover it with certainty.

Server-based imputation services such as the Michigan Imputation Server include extensive automated quality control that compares the input file to the reference panel and applies corrections where mismatches are detected. In the test sample, the Michigan TOPMed pipeline reported zero strand flips and zero allele switches required, suggesting either that the input file was correctly encoded in this respect or that the server's automated corrections handled the discrepancies internally. Local pipelines without access to the manifest cannot offer equivalent guarantees.

I attempted to obtain manifest information from a research group that had published results from a similar custom GSA-based platform. The request was not answered. I note this not as a complaint but as illustration of a structural issue in the field: manifests for custom DTC arrays are typically treated by manufacturers as commercial confidential information, and the academic users of such data often have no mechanism for accessing the manifest, even through informal collaboration with other research groups working with the same platform.

6. TOPMed imputation quality by PRS model

To assess whether the high aggregate imputation quality reported for the TOPMed panel (median $DR^2 = 0.99$ across all scored variants) translates to adequate per-model quality for the PRS computed in this study, the info.gz files returned by the Michigan Imputation Server were analysed separately for each of the principal models. Results are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Per-model imputation quality from TOPMed info.gz files. N matched: number of variants from the model

that could be identified in the imputed file. Coverage: percentage of model variants matched.

Model	N in model	N matched	Coverage	Median DR ²	% DR ² > 0.3	% DR ² > 0.8
ADHD (Demontis et al., 2023)	52,329	40,737	77.8%	0.000	30.1%	29.4%
Autism spectrum disorder	916,647	728,176	79.4%	1.000	56.2%	55.5%
Schizophrenia	964,355	765,638	79.4%	1.000	55.9%	55.2%
Major depressive disorder	1,088,405	863,134	79.3%	1.000	52.4%	51.8%
Neuroticism (PGS002342)	1,109,252	878,194	79.2%	1.000	52.2%	51.6%
Neuroticism (PGS004608)	1,000,446	793,621	79.3%	1.000	54.5%	53.8%

For five of the six models, the median DR² of matched variants is 1.0, indicating that more than half of the variants used in the score are either directly genotyped on the array or imputed with very high confidence. The DR² distribution is bimodal: approximately 55% of variants have DR² ≈ 1.0 (typed or well-imputed), and approximately 44% have DR² ≈ 0 (rare variants poorly represented in the reference panel's haplotypes for this sample).

The Demontis et al. 2023 ADHD model is the exception. The median DR² is 0.0 despite 77.8% coverage of the model. This reflects the genetic architecture of ADHD as captured by this particular GWAS: the model contains a disproportionate number of low-MAF variants that do not impute well from chip array data regardless of reference panel size. Only 30% of the model's variants exceed DR² > 0.3, leaving approximately 12,000 of 52,329 variants for filtered scoring. Whether this filtered subset constitutes a representative sample of the full model - or whether systematic bias is introduced by selection on imputation quality - is a separate methodological question that I address in a companion technical note.

7. Validation of TOPMed results

Several lines of evidence support treating the TOPMed-imputed results as reliable for this sample.

First, the QC report returned by the Michigan Imputation Server records zero variants requiring strand flip and zero requiring allele switch. This indicates either that the input file was correctly encoded in these respects or that the server's automated procedures resolved any discrepancies before imputation.

Second, in a controlled experiment in which Michigan TOPMed and Michigan HRC imputations were compared on an identical set of SNPs (the intersection of variants present in both imputed files), the Z-score differences for the three models tested (SCZ, ADHD Demontis, ASD) were all below 0.8. Such concordance between two independent reference panels is difficult to achieve under conditions of systematic input error.

Third, the median DR² of 0.99 for scored variants is uniform across the genome rather than bimodal at the per-chromosome level, which would be the expected signature of a systematic encoding error affecting some but not all chromosomes.

I conducted a direct validation experiment by re-submitting the input file to the Michigan Imputation Server with 4,119 anchor SNPs masked. These were SNPs called with high confidence on the original array, with MAF > 0.10 in 1KGP EUR, non-palindromic, and evenly distributed across the genome. The two imputation runs - original (full input) and masked (anchors removed) - produced PRS Z-scores differing by $\Delta z \leq 0.01$ for all ten tested models, demonstrating reproducibility of the imputation procedure. The median DR² for masked anchor SNPs in the resulting TOPMed info file was 0.907, with 51.5% of anchors at DR² > 0.9. The remaining 37.6% had DR² < 0.3, corresponding to anchor SNPs without strong LD proxies in the TOPMed panel for this individual - an expected limitation of array-to-WGS imputation regardless of reference size.

8. Local BEAGLE+1KGP for low-coverage sequencing data

The 1KGP reference panel that is inadequate for chip array imputation may nonetheless be adequate for imputation of low-coverage whole-genome sequencing (lcWGS) data. The two problems are not equivalent. Algorithms such as GLIMPSE2 (Rubinacci et al., 2023) operate on read-level genotype likelihoods rather than on imputed dosages from a sparse set of array probes. For each position in the genome, the algorithm has direct evidence from the reads that overlap that position, weighted by their quality scores. The reference panel is used to infer haplotype structure and to fill in gaps where read coverage is insufficient, rather than as the primary source of information.

In benchmarks against deep WGS, GLIMPSE2 with the 1KGP panel achieves $DR^2 > 0.9$ for common variants at coverage of 2–3×, comparable to chip array data imputed against larger reference panels (Rubinacci et al., 2023). For populations underrepresented in current arrays, lcWGS at 4× coverage has been shown to detect 95% of common variants and 45% of singletons found in deep WGS, at a cost comparable to high-density genotyping arrays (Martin et al., 2021).

Data from the first volunteers in the pre-pilot phase of an ongoing study are currently being sequenced as lcWGS at 2–3× depth on the Ultima Genomics UG100 platform. To my knowledge no published benchmark has yet evaluated the combination of Ultima Genomics output with GLIMPSE2 imputation specifically for PRS calculation, and this pilot will therefore also serve as a methodological check of pipeline behaviour on a sequencing platform whose error profile differs systematically from the Illumina platforms on which GLIMPSE2 was originally benchmarked. UG100 shows higher total variant-calling errors than NovaSeqX in benchmark regions, primarily driven by indel false negatives and coverage dropouts in GC-rich regions (Risse-Adams et al., 2026), but for common-variant PRS applications, where SNV calling rather than indel detection is the limiting factor, the impact on imputation quality is expected to be modest. Results from this benchmarking exercise will be reported in a separate methodological note.

9. Recommendations

Direct-to-consumer chip array data. Use server-based imputation (Michigan TOPMed or HRC). Results from local BEAGLE imputation with reference panels smaller than approximately 50,000 samples should be considered unreliable for this data type, particularly when the array manifest is not publicly available.

Data transfer concerns. The University of Michigan provides a standard Data Processing Agreement for European researchers, and post-imputation data are retained on Michigan servers for a limited period (typically 72 hours after download). Subsequent standardisation against a population reference does not require data transfer.

Low-coverage whole-genome sequencing. GLIMPSE2 with a local 1KGP reference is appropriate for sample coverage in the range 1–4×. At higher coverage, larger reference panels (HRC, TOPMed) become beneficial for rare-variant accuracy but are not required for common-variant PRS.

Pipeline-agnostic quality validation. Regardless of the imputation method employed, an external validation procedure can be used to verify imputation behaviour on a specific dataset. The procedure consists of selecting a random subset of approximately 5,000 SNPs that are well-called on the input, non-palindromic, and of $MAF > 0.10$; masking these positions before imputation; and comparing the imputed dosages with the original genotypes after imputation. The Pearson r^2 between observed and imputed values at the per-SNP level indicates how much of the imputation output represents real information rather than population-mean substitution. Suggested thresholds: median $r^2 > 0.90$ across SNPs and $r^2 > 0.95$ for PRS computed on these SNPs as acceptable quality criteria. This procedure is informative when DR^2 is in the intermediate range (0.3–0.8), where internal quality metrics alone may not distinguish true imputation from regression to the population mean. At very low $DR^2 (< 0.05)$, as observed for the local BEAGLE+1KGP pipeline described here, the outcome of the anchor test is predictable and the test adds little information beyond the DR^2 distribution itself.

10. Conclusions

The Z-scores produced by local BEAGLE+1KGP imputation of DTC chip array data are unreliable. The corrected version of the pipeline, with the technical errors of Section 3 resolved, achieves median DR² of approximately 0.04 across scored variants, which is too low to support meaningful PRS computation. The results from server-based TOPMed imputation are, on the evidence available, reliable for this sample and serve as the reference for further analysis.

The principal methodological contribution of this work is the explicit distinction between *in silico* GSA data, simulated by extracting array positions from existing sequence-derived genotypes, and real DTC data from arrays with proprietary manifests. The two situations are superficially similar - both produce a file of genotypes at chip-array-density positions - but they differ fundamentally with respect to the feasibility of local allele harmonisation, the verifiability of strand and allele assignments, and the consequent reliability of any pipeline that does not employ external automated quality control. Pipelines validated on *in silico* data should not be assumed to perform equivalently on real DTC data, and this assumption appears to be widespread in the field.

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Bioinformatic analyses were performed on the author's private computational infrastructure (AMD EPYC 7R13 server, 256 GB RAM, dedicated NVMe storage). Server-based imputation was performed via the Michigan Imputation Server using the TOPMed r3 reference panel. Pipeline code is available from the author on request. Large language models (Anthropic Claude, Moonshot Kimi) were used as assistants during analysis, debugging, and manuscript drafting. The author takes full responsibility for the content of this manuscript.

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